

Review of *36 Views of Mount Fuji (36 vistas del monte Fuji)* by Sans Soleil Ediciones

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BOOK DETAILS

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- **EDITION TITLE (SPANISH):** *36 vistas del monte Fuji*
- **TITLE FOR ENGLISH READERS:** *36 Views of Mount Fuji*
- **AUTHOR:** Katsushika Hokusai —1760–1849—. Edited by Vicente David Almazán Tomás —1971—
- **TRANSLATION (SPANISH):** Vicente David Almazán Tomás. Texts revised by Isabel Mellén
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Cover of Hokusai's *36 Views of Mount Fuji*, by Sans Soleil Ediciones

A New Approach to the Timeless Work of Katsushika Hokusai

The Spanish publishing house Sans Soleil, based in Vitoria-Gasteiz, released the Spanish edition of this book in October 2019. It is number 19 in the Wunderkammer collection —German for “cabinet of wonders”— dedicated to both visual works and silent novels, as well as the work of printmakers, illustrators, and engravers.

Specifically, *36 Views of Mount Fuji* belongs to the publisher's Japan series: a set of publications specialised in bringing the works of Japan's great masters to wider attention in Spain.

This volume presents a compendium of some of Katsushika Hokusai's most celebrated works, both in the West and in Japan. By the time this review was written in 2021, it was the publisher's most recent edition of the master's work. Over the years, Sans Soleil has also released other Hokusai-related volumes, such as *One Hundred Views of Mount Fuji (Cien vistas del Monte Fuji, 2016)*, reviewed by Sergio Paterna, and *Abridged Drawing Manual (Manual de dibujo abreviado, 2018)*, reviewed by the present author for CoolJapan.es.

Hokusai is internationally recognised and studied by artists and art historians alike. Yet his fame is not limited to modern times; he was already admired by art enthusiasts centuries ago, not only in his native country. His frequent use of flat colour —taking advantage of traditional print colouring techniques—, his decomposition of subjects into simple geometric forms, his use of perspective as a visual language, and his meticulous compositional study, have made him a subject of study for other great artists such as Monet, Cézanne, Degas, and even van Gogh.

Hokusai became well-known in Europe and beyond through the phenomenon known as Japonisme, whereby Japanese art began to be collected and studied in the West during the nineteenth century. As Almazán notes throughout this book, this influence persists today, extending not only to Hokusai's pictorial works but also to anime, manga, and video games.

Katsushika Hokusai is remembered not only as a renowned artist but also as a highly skilled craftsman and master of the arts. Through his works and the publications accompanying them, he teaches readers and viewers how to produce and understand art, particularly drawing. This is evident in his celebrated volumes, *Manga*, which provide lessons on drawing and composition, as well as in works such as the aforementioned *Abridged Drawing Manual*, reviewed by the author for CoolJapan.es.

Almazán notes of the master that he “was capable of drawing anything,” a claim amply demonstrated by following the professor's explanations alongside Hokusai's own works and their relation to his other productions and instructional manuals.

Hokusai's work continues to be studied in design and art schools, employed by educators to teach drawing —something the reviewer can personally attest to, as he uses books like this with his own students to learn to draw.

The master drew upon his own talent and techniques, further developed through studying the work of other great artists, including ukiyo-e masters such as Nishikawa Sukenobu (1671–1750) and Suzuki Harunobu (1724–1770). Additionally, he incorporated Western techniques, such as linear perspective, introduced to Japan by foreign merchants and missionaries —known as *nanban*, primarily Portuguese and Dutch— long before Hokusai's birth.

This image shows a self-portrait attributed to an elderly Hokusai, as reproduced in this book.

This illustration accompanies several pages detailing significant aspects of the master's life.

Hokusai used these techniques as just another element in his personal artistic language. In his work, he also paid homage to one artist or another, always seeking originality in parallel—although, as Almazán notes in this book, the master sometimes even “plagiarised himself,” repeating certain motifs or models in various works due, for example, to a fixation on a particular situation or character.

Katsushika Hokusai is an example of a person belonging to the urban commoner class, known as *chōnin*—which, with due caution, we can compare to the lower and middle classes in Europe, encompassing people such as merchants or artisans. As in the West, popular-consumption art—the kind to which the *ukiyo-e* genre belongs, intended for mass reproduction, and in which Hokusai specialised—eventually gained prestige and came to be studied and respected for its true artistic and craft value. The master never enjoyed great wealth, but he did achieve certain renown in various towns, fulfilling a multitude of commissions.

Hokusai's international fame came posthumously. Many contemporary and later painters, illustrators, and curators, such as Toulouse-Lautrec, included the Japanese master's works in their personal collections. This recognition coincided with the end of the *sakoku* policies established by the Tokugawa shogunate, which had restricted Japan's contact with the outside world, and allowed foreigners to communicate with the Japanese without the strict control of the *bakufu*—the type of government led by a *shōgun*, which remained in place until the disappearance of the samurai in the nineteenth century.

Katsushika Hokusai did not live or behave like a contemporary Western artist as we understand it today, but rather like an artisan. He was also an inquisitive and curious individual, constantly learning and developing his skills, travelling and exploring his own country. While he enjoyed some renown during his lifetime, he never fully detached from the lower and middle classes, and his work consistently pays tribute to their daily lives and occupations.

This edition also features material written by Professor David Almazán—just as with other Sans Soleil publications—who provides an exhaustive explanation of these aspects, putting the reader in context as they view the images throughout the pages.

Hokusai's most famous works, together in *36 Views of Mount Fuji*

This *36 Views of Mount Fuji* represents a full exercise and demonstration of what a journey means. And not only in the literal sense—which also applies—but as a spiritual journey. The importance of Mount Fuji—富士山 or *Fujisan* in Japanese—goes beyond being the highest mountain in the country, standing at a respectable 3,776 metres. The mountain holds spiritual and religious significance for the Japanese people, being associated with both *Shintō* and Buddhist beliefs—especially the latter, with the first documented ascent made by an anonymous Buddhist monk in the seventh century CE.

Its shape is considered the closest to perfection by the Japanese.

In Hokusai's time and earlier, pilgrimage to Mount Fuji had vital importance for people across Japan. Samurai troops trained near its base, great leaders such as shōgun Minamoto no Yoritomo practised horseback archery in the area, important daimyō like Takeda Shingen are historically connected to the region (the former province of Kai), countless artists wrote poems inspired by the mountain, and the area hosts significant temples such as Fujisan Hongū Sengen Taisha (Shintō) and Taiseki-ji (Buddhist).

Visiting Mount Fuji was a test of both courage and effort, but also an opportunity to value and appreciate the journey itself and the views from the summit. Hokusai was particularly fascinated by its topography—which is evident in every print in this book—the geometric forms he could deconstruct and relate to each image, its symbolism, and he could not avoid using Fuji in earlier compositions not only as a stylistic and compositional resource but also as a crucial element in many of his works. Of course, these views of Fuji are not the last works Hokusai produced, but they are the most famous.

This book is not simply a collection of 36 images featuring the mountain. This compendium has a much deeper significance, which is further enhanced in this Spanish edition through the texts that explain each work and situate them in context. The idea for this collection was conceived by Hokusai together with his publisher, Nishimuraya Yohachi, with whom he had collaborated many times and had developed a mutual trust over the years.

Yohachi's plan, through his prestigious Eijudō publishing house, was to take advantage of a newly arrived formula for creating Prussian blue pigment —“Berliner Blau” in German, invented by Heinrich Diesbach in Berlin in 1704, reaching Japan more than a century later— to produce a series of prints in which blue predominated. This printing technique in blue is known as 藍摺絵 —*aizuri-e*.

Hokusai, not only a draughtsman but also a professional printmaker, worked closely with the editorial team to endow the woodblock prints—one of the oldest printing methods in the world, popular in Japan and used in ukiyo-e—with a unique spirit. In the various works he produced for this series, this is evident at every turn, with blue even used for contours and silhouettes, and showing unparalleled mastery in the use of transitions and transparencies with this colour.

This is all captured thoughtfully in the present edition.

This image corresponds to the print *Ejiri, Suruga Province* —駿州江尻, or *Sunshū Ejiri*—

The result is what one would expect from an artist of Hokusai's talent and capabilities, and it manifested in legendary works such as *The Great Wave off Kanagawa*, *Red Fuji*, or *Storm Beneath the Summit*. However, these three were not the only notable pieces in the entire compendium, as will become apparent as one begins to explore and enjoy this book.

Hokusai was always renowned for his treatment of human and animal figures in his works, as well as for introducing subtle allusions, anecdotes, and even small jokes, making a landscape show not only natural elements but also the interaction of humans and animals within the scene.

Through this approach, the master succeeded not only in entertaining the viewer and producing a varied oeuvre—considering how challenging it was to establish a presence in a market saturated with countless depictions of Mount Fuji and other typical Japanese landscapes and landmarks, which were commonplace during Hokusai's lifetime—but also, by extension, in creating a visual narrative that conveys the Japan of his time, its customs, and the various social classes inhabiting it. This grants Hokusai's work extraordinary cultural value, beyond the purely technical or artistic.

In each print, one does not merely see any horse placed to embellish the scene, but an animal that has lost a horseshoe, another that refuses to continue along the path, or several carrying messengers at full speed—illustrating why these animals appear in that specific print. There is always a narrative and a rationale behind Hokusai's compositions.

Everything is positioned with intent—sometimes simply to create a novel and striking composition. One sees samurai and their escorts marching or practising falconry, peasants interacting with warriors, children playing with their pets, and people so absorbed in their daily tasks that, even with a beautiful view of Mount Fuji nearby, they scarcely glance at the majestic volcano, lest a work-related mishap occur.

The editor did not conceive the *36 Views* as a fixed number—the thirty-six is more symbolic in Japan—but rather as a collection that could be expanded. Indeed, the original edition’s success led Nishimuraya Yohachi to commission Hokusai to create ten additional prints for a later edition. On this occasion, Hokusai worked with black outlines and included more human figures. The Spanish edition under review encompasses both the original thirty-six views and the ten subsequently added.

A Spanish edition reflecting utmost respect for Hokusai’s Japan

The graphic design and layout were carried out by Habemus Estudio. Their work is integrated with Hokusai’s prints and Almazán’s explanatory texts, offering a meticulous presentation of each piece. Both the volume’s overall presentation and its internal structure exemplify reverence for the Japanese master’s work.

This respect begins with the format itself: horizontal, as Hokusai employed for his original prints. Consequently, each view occupies nearly the full page, fully capturing the reader’s gaze.

The cover features, naturally, what is considered Hokusai’s masterpiece and one of the greatest works in the art world, which also appears inside the book: *The Great Wave off Kanagawa*, which commands immediate attention. The endpapers display another work by Hokusai, *Uneri no Fuji (The Fuji of the Waves)*, from a different collection—the second volume of *One Hundred Views of Mount Fuji*, produced after the *Thirty-six Views of Mount Fuji*.

On these pages, which serve as an introduction to the various Fuji prints, Almazán has indicated the different locations where Hokusai placed each view —whether he actually visited them or not— both in the city of Edo (modern-day Tokyo) and in the other towns and provinces of Japan where Fuji appears in the prints shown later in the book.

Even the Japanese title appears on the cover, alongside the Eijudō publisher’s mon —emblem— on the colophon, giving the impression of a Japanese edition of the *36 Views*. Hokusai often included subtle references to this publisher within the prints, sometimes incorporating advertisements, as David Almazán reveals throughout the commentary.

The edition employs a hardcover binding, lending the book visual weight and durability. Despite its horizontal format, substantial binding, and page count, the book is remarkably light in hand—a fact confirmed after long hours spent examining Hokusai’s prints.

Matte paper with a slight texture is used, providing proper whiteness and excellent contrast between light and dark, facilitating the reading of accompanying text —set in a serif typeface designed for legibility. The non-glossy surface ensures that every detail in Hokusai’s works is perceptible, allowing one to distinguish between various tones, shades, and lighting. No printing errors were found, and colours are faithfully reproduced. The key blue hues central to these Mount Fuji views are rendered with particular care, including outlines made in blue by the artist and editorial team.

Almazán's commentary enriches Hokusai's oeuvre

An added value in this Spanish edition of *36 Views of Mount Fuji* is the thorough work of Dr Vicente David Almazán Tomás, a professor of Japanese art at the University of Zaragoza, who guides the reader through the collection as he does in other Sans Soleil publications on Japanese art.

The book opens with a concise introduction by Almazán, detailing much of Hokusai's life, professional and editorial career, and—crucially—providing context for the images. While the *36 Views*—actually 46—represent a journey, so too does the introduction, preparing the reader to analyse the collection print by print. Almazán discusses the immeasurable significance of the Nihonbashi Bridge, Edo city, its connection with Hokusai and ukiyo-e, Mount Fuji, and various districts, locations, and key roads of Hokusai's Japan—such as the Tōkaidō and Kōshū Kaidō—from which the mountain could be viewed. He explains what can be seen in each print, detailing characters' behaviour, routines, and appearance.

The sequence of prints was chosen by Almazán, establishing thematic or regional connections, though the reader may navigate the edition freely. Almazán also cross-references the same term, situation, or object across different prints to reinforce understanding.

Although one may enjoy the book without reading Almazán's texts, doing so greatly enhances appreciation, revealing why each composition was conceived in a particular way. Almazán never considers a print in isolation but always situates it in relation to other works by Hokusai, as well as the broader artistic dialogue with predecessors, contemporaries, and successors. Most importantly, the introductory text and the commentary accompanying each print allow readers—including those with little prior knowledge of Japan—to understand aspects of Japanese art and culture, as well as social structures, celebrations, customs, professions, and behaviours depicted in Hokusai's works.

In this series of images, David Almazán highlights details of the composition of several prints from this collection, as well as various aspects related to the geometric elements and specific uses of perspective that Hokusai employed when drawing and composing.

It is also worth mentioning that Almazán's style of expression is highly accessible, avoiding the use of excessive technical jargon —and when such terms are employed, he defines and explains them accordingly, as is the case with the numerous Japanese-origin words appearing in this book. The professor consistently uses language that is close to the reader, and often seeks to establish bridges between Japanese and Western culture, facilitating understanding through these connections.

Almazán explains how the artist created the prints, who and what appears in them, and why they are represented in the manner they are, as well as the symbolism associated with each element in each work. We come to understand the significance of cranes depicted in a particular way, the meaning of a kite shaped like a specific animal, and dozens of other elements explained by the author throughout these pages. All of this allows us to imagine what Hokusai's Japan was like, teaching us at every step during the enjoyable pilgrimage to Mount Fuji that reading this volume becomes.

Average rating: 93/100

- **Literary quality:** 95/100
- **Narrative fluency:** 95/100
- **Edition:** 95/100
- **Reading accessibility:** 85/100
- **Overall relevance:** 95/100

36 Views of Mount Fuji

A completely essential work for lovers of Japanese art, yet also highly recommended for those unfamiliar with Japanese culture and art, as it allows readers, guided by David Almazán, to approach Hokusai's Japan and the artist's work. A superb edition, comfortable and enjoyable to read, providing both a visual and intellectual delight. The love for the master artist's work is palpable, and the team at CoolJapan.es hopes it will help newcomers engage with Katsushika Hokusai's oeuvre in the best possible way, starting with some of his masterpieces, meticulously explained in this book. This volume will inspire readers to undertake a pilgrimage to the renowned Mount Fuji, if they had not already felt the desire.

Sources

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